

Exposure and Response to Media Discourses on Plastic Pollution Among State Civil Servants in South-East Nigeria

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Abstract

Against the backdrop of high rate of environmental pollution in the lives of humans, this study examines exposure and response to media discourses on plastic pollution among state civil servants in South-East Nigeria. The study was quantitative in nature and was guided by four research questions; To what extent are state civil servants in South-East Nigeria exposed to media discourses on plastic pollution; What are the exact media discourses on plastic pollution which the civil servants are exposed to? What readings do the civil servants give to media discourses on plastic pollution? How have media discourses on plastic pollution influenced environmental practices of the civil servants? 500 sample size was chosen for the study while a structured questionnaire was the data collection instrument. Situated within the context of encoding and decoding theory, the study found that state civil servants in South-East Nigeria were exposed to media discourses on plastic pollution specifically via radio, television, newspapers and the Internet, with the Internet, however, being the recurring channel. The study further found that the specific discourses the civil servants were exposed largely related to the causes, dangers, and measures against plastic pollution. The study recommends that environmental campaign (especially in relation to plastic pollution) in South-East geopolitical zone and indeed all parts of Nigeria should emphasize adoption of recommended actions and the benefits of so doing.

Keywords: Media, Pollution, Civil Servants

Introduction

Plastic pollution and its short and long term effect on human habitat and health have been a leading issue in the current global concern regarding the sustainability of the environment (United Nations Environment

Programme, 2018; Rochman, Hoh, Kurobe & Teh, 2013). In Nigeria, this concern is made more urgent by the fact that the nation, unlike the developed countries of the world, is yet to evolve an adequate and efficient mechanism for managing this class of non-biodegradable waste (Otu & Oloidi, 2018; United Nations Environment Programme, 2018; Lavers & Bond, 2017; Kadafa, Ayuba & Idris, 2017; Aderogba, 2014).

The world over, public campaigns have been going on to educate people and positively influence their attitudes and behaviour regarding plastic pollution and other environmental issues (United Nations Environment Programme, 2018; Lavers & Bond, 2017). Instructively, the mass media have been frequently deployed in aid of this effort (Mbalisi & Offor, 2012). Literature in Nigeria (see Miller, 2011; Aderogba, 2014; Moharam & Maher, 2014; Adekomaya & Ojo, 2016; Kadafa, Ayuba & Idris, 2017) shows that while media's role in public education on the environmental issues generally has been variously studied, little appears to have been done specifically in regard to plastic waste and plastic pollution. Against this backdrop, this research will focus on exposure and response to media Discourses on plastic pollution among civil servants in South-East Nigeria.

Waste is an unavoidable phenomenon in human existence being that human activities inevitably produce it (United Nations Environment Programme, 2018; Lavers & Bond, 2017). Aderogba (2014) observes that waste exists in various forms and types and its presence has constituted a significant concern to humanity given that waste management is often a complex endeavour and which may be quite demanding in terms of planning, coordination and financing. Therefore, individuals, communities, governments, organisations and research bodies have continuously explored ways of managing and addressing the challenge posed by waste to human development (Aderogba, 2014).

Prior to the industrial revolution, people's needs were more basic, thus the consumption patterns and waste patterns were predictable. Even though management of waste still posed a problem at this time, the magnitude was definitely low. With the industrial revolution came technological advancements, and with that the emergence of new sources of waste which generated waste in such magnitude and form that increasingly make waste management quite complex. Added to this is geometrically increasing populations, growing urbanization and changing consumption culture, which have all intensified the modern challenge of waste management (Kadafa, Ayuba & Idris, 2017).

In terms of their speed and pattern of breaking down, waste is generally classified into degradable and non-degradable. Other classifications categorise waste as solid, liquid and gaseous; radioactive and non-radioactive waste; animal and plant waste; domestic, industrial, hospital, commercial, agricultural, celebrations, and decorations waste among others (Otu & Oloidi, 2018). Based on all this, Print, Chen and Patel (as cited in Aderogba, 2014) define waste as "leftovers, excesses, surpluses, unwanted and remains that are discarded, castoff, rejected, superfluous, dumped and or thrown away" (p.82). One common character of waste of all kinds is that they are unwanted materials, at least at the particular moment in

question. Secondly, all waste is an outcome of processes of production and or transformation of some material resources from one form to another. Nonetheless, there are some schools of thought that believe that there is no material entity that is absolutely a waste. In this respect, it means such materials are only awaiting more purposeful uses or that there are no yet technologies of developing them into useful states or entity (Aderogba, as cited in Print *et al.*, 2012). Thus, Aderogba (2012) observes that used tyres, for instance, may not be regarded as waste. In other words, wastes are the remnants of productions, processing, non-serviceability, disuse and others that have been discarded and abandoned for wants of immediate use.

Statement of the Problem

The management of solid wastes has, in recent time, been a serious challenge globally with Nigeria not being an exception (Otu & Oloidi, 2018; Mbalisi & Offor, 2012). The country is also heavily burdened by plastic pollution as plastic wastes accumulate uncontrollably in the absence of recycling plants and other management mechanisms (United Nations Environment Programme, 2018; Kadafa, Ayuba & Idris, 2017; Aderogba, 2014).

The discourse on the dangers of accumulation of plastic waste (i.e. plastic pollution) and measures against it has gone on for a couple of years now including in the media. Like other media messages, this discourse is expected to increase public awareness and understanding of this phenomenon as well as bring about attitudinal and behaviour change towards a healthier environment (United Nations Environment Programme, 2018). However, there is evidence that indiscriminate disposal of plastic waste (and indeed other forms of waste) has continued to prevail in Nigeria (United Nations Environment Programme, 2018; Alabi, Ologbonjaye, Awosolu & Alalade, 2019; Kadafa, Ayuba & Idris, 2017; Aderogba, 2014) bringing to question the effectiveness of this discourse as a source of public enlightenment. Are the people exposed to this discourse? If yes, why does improper plastic waste disposal seem to persist?

Local studies on plastic pollution (see Aderogba, 2014; Adekomaya & Ojo, 2016; Kadafa *et al.*, 2017) have focused mainly on plastic waste management without looking at the communication dimension. However, studies on audience response to environmental communication (such as Ononeze & Okoroafor, 2018; Obuah & Okon, 2017; Nabegu & Mustapha, Akpoghiran, 2015; 2014; Akpoghiran & Okoro, 2014) have focused generally on issues such as climate change, solid waste management and e-waste management with little attention paid to plastic waste specifically. This makes a study on audience exposure and response to issues of plastic waste and plastic pollution relevant.

Research Questions

In line with the above objectives, the following research questions guided the study:

1. To what extent are state civil servants in South-East Nigeria exposed to media discourses on plastic pollution?

2. What are the exact media discourses on plastic pollution which the civil servants are exposed to?
3. What readings do the civil servants give to media discourses on plastic pollution?
4. How have media discourses on plastic pollution influenced environmental practices of the civil servants?

Scope of the Study

This study focused on exposure and response to media discourses on plastic pollution among state civil servants in South-East Nigeria. Data collection and analysis was restricted to the four variables in the research objectives viz: exposure to media discourses on plastic pollution, exact media discourses exposed to; audience reading of media discourses on plastic pollution; and influence of media discourses on environmental behaviour.

Furthermore, data collections was restricted to state civil servants in the South-East. Literature shows that studies related to audience response to media environmental campaigns have mainly focused on other regions of the country as against the South-East (Ononeze & Okoroafor, 2018; Obuah & Okon, 2017; Nabegu & Mustapha, Akpoghiran, 2015; 2014; Akpoghiran & Okoro, 2014)

Review Of Related Literature

Safe disposal of waste and the role of the mass media in influencing audience behaviour in this regard have been a subject of scholarly discourse over the years. Thus, scholars have continued to engage the question of whether and how the media affect people's awareness, knowledge and practice in regard to healthy disposal of waste. Therefore, this chapter reviews literature related to the subject of this dissertation in the conceptual, empirical and theoretical sense.

Miller (2011) examined attitude and action of students in regard to single-use plastic shopping bag on the university of Alabama campus. The research was designed as a survey and questionnaire was administered to 162 students on campus to assess attitudes and behaviours related to plastic bags, reusable shopping bags, and related human-environmental issues. Findings showed students' dominant attitude toward single-use plastic bags was not consistent with dominant behaviour or how they used plastic bags, also, the existing stimuli in many retail environments were strong enough that students generally used plastic bags despite conflicting attitudes. The study similarly found that though the students were aware of problems associated with plastic bags, these items were a valued part of some students' shopping experiences. Lastly, it was found that a store discount for using reusable bags when checking out may be the best stimulus to derive consistency between student attitude and student behaviour in regard to single-use plastic shopping bags.

Aderogba (2014) assessed the quantity and effects of polymer wastes in the cities and towns around Nigeria. The plants and facilities for manufacturing were visited with the observation method applied for collecting data. Market women and polymer dealers were also interviewed on the quantity sold per month/year, wastes generated, and challenges and means of addressing the challenges. Directors in the state ministries of environment were similarly interviewed on the enormity of plastic wastes and their impact. A dump each in 30 Nigerian cities and towns were studied for ten years; 2003 – 2012. Composition, quantity and spread of plastic wastes were examined. Impacts were studied and compared with European cities. 80 photographic snaps were taken of polymer wastes and sceneries of visible consequences. Findings showed that on the average, polymer wastes constituted 28.00% of the wastes found at dumps and around streets, residential, recreational and other public places. The concentrations were highest at recreation and residential areas. They were non-degradable; and every moment, there were additions. On the average, less than 12% were recycled annually even though the recycling was not absolute. There were neither special technologies nor policies and programmes for special collection, transportation and disposal as obtained in most of the European cities and towns. The study concluded that government in Nigeria may have to borrow leaves from Europe and invest massively on research and development and campaign for reducing, reusing and recycling the polymer wastes.

Adekomaya and Ojo (2016) assessed the adaptation of plastic waste to energy development in Lagos State. The researchers examined government reports for the months of January, July and September, 2014 regarding plastic waste management. Findings showed that volume of wastes for the month of January, July and September, 2014 were 340,016.62m and 298791.81m respectively with plastic waste accounting, on the whole, for over 35%. Thus, there was high volume of plastic waste generated. The study, however, further found that there was not efficient machinery in place to manage this waste particularly in the context of energy renewal. The researchers concluded that although government appeared to be making spirited efforts to reduce waste volume to considerable size, there seemed to be some difficult obstacles ahead.

Kadafa, Ayuba and Idris (2017) examined mixed plastic waste in Abuja, Nigeria and its environmental hazards. The survey method was employed and 400 questionnaire copies were administered to residents of Abuja. The results showed that only 43% of residents had access to waste collection services, with infrequent collections. Correspondingly, a high percentage of the residents (65.7% used dumping as a method of disposing their waste, resulting in accumulation of plastic waste which causes litter of the environment. These mixed plastics are non-biodegradable and therefore could not be used as compost by the local communities and Government did not also seem to possess the capacity to recycle them.

Adetusi and Obrota (2008) investigated the extent to which the print media, and particularly the newspapers, reported environmental and rural development information and specialty issues in 2006. The researchers analyzed five leading national newspapers for a period of twelve months. Findings showed that coverage

of rural development was highest (31.48%) in the fourth quarter, and least in the third quarter (17.79%) of the year. Sixty nine percent of rural development information/news appeared as features, while others were presented as editorials (13.04%), advertorials (9.27%) and pictorials (8.38%). *The Sun* newspapers (23.65%) could easily pass as the best print medium in reporting environmental and rural development news, followed by *The Punch* (22.5%) and *Daily Champion* (21.3%) newspapers. *The Sun* newspapers also exhibited consistent leadership in promoting activities in the health and population/family planning sub-sectors, while *Daily Champion* disseminated more information on rural infrastructure and environmental matters.

Akpan, Anorue and Ukonu (2012) assessed the influence of Nigerian media on public knowledge of climate change. The researchers sought to ascertain the specific ways in which Nigerian media reportage of climate change had affected public knowledge of the subject matter. A survey was conducted in Abuja, Enugu, Ikeja and Port Harcourt. Editors of four newspapers in Nigeria were interviewed. Results indicated that the mass media did not rank the highest as sources of information for the audience on climate change, and they (media) did not significantly influence public knowledge of climate change. The researchers observed that this finding differed from results of studies in the US where the media had been found to exert visible influence on people's knowledge and understanding of climate change issues.

The research by Batta, Ashong and Bashir (2013) focused on Nigerian press coverage of climate change issues in the country as well as the implications of this for public participation opportunities. The study involved content analysis of systematically sampled 438 issues from 4,380 issues of four purposively selected daily newspapers between 2007 and 2009. Findings showed that climate politics/economics issues (61.2%) dominated coverage, while foreign sources were the dominant origin of reports (63.4%). Further, majority of the reports (83.6%) came as straight news, while framing in terms of mitigation was dominant (55.2%) i.e. mitigation efforts aim to reduce or prevent emission of greenhouse gases. The study concluded that coverage and framing constrain opportunities for popular participation in climate change discourse.

Ogunjinmi, Onadeko and Ogunjinmi (2013) studied media coverage of nature conservation and protection in Nigeria national parks. Five newspapers; *The Punch*, *Nigerian Tribune*, *The Nation*, *The Vanguard* and *The Guardian*; and four broadcast houses; Edo Broadcasting Service (EBS-Television), Taraba Television Corporation (TTV), Edo Radio and Federal Radio Corporation of Nigeria (FRCN) Ibadan national station were sampled. The broadcast organisations were selected based on the states where national parks are located. Articles in the selected print media and programmes on the sampled electronic media which related to nature conservation/protection and other environmental issues were analyzed. Results showed that 316 articles were published on environmental issues by the print media. *The Guardian* newspaper published the highest number of articles with 257 articles. Articles on nature conservation and protection featured least. On the other hand, broadcast media had no specific programmes on nature conservation. The researchers

concluded that there will be an increase in public awareness, knowledge, appreciation of parks' resources, and policy support for biodiversity conservation efforts if synergy can be achieved between Nigeria National Parks Service and major media establishments.

Theoretical Framework

The Audience Reception Theory will be adopted for developing a theoretical framework for this study. This theory was first put forwards by Paul Stuart Hall in 1973 via his popular essay "Encoding and Decoding in the Television Discourse". In this essay, Hall describes how the audience play a role in the effect of a message communicated by virtue of how they decode i.e. receive such message (Hall, 1973).

Hall's theory was based on his modification of the Reception Theory of Hans-Robert Juass. The idea of audience reception as espoused by Juass was very simple and straightforward: a message would be created and sent, and an audience would accept and understand the media or text when a group of readers had a shared cultural background or interpretation with the text and media in similar ways as the author (Nightingale, 2011). Hall, however, observed that the major problem with Juass's theory is that it is very unlikely for an audience to have similar or shared reactions if they did not have anything in common with the author; in other words, their personal experience would vary person to person and be completely different, thus carrying their interpretation of the author's intended encoding. In other words, an encoded message does not basically possess any inherent meaning but that it is the audience who read meaning into it (Hall, 1973).

Hall (1973) tried to explain the relationship between the sender and the receiver, arguing that there are a number of significant steps involved in the sending and receiving of a message. He believes that the audience plays a large part in the success of message delivery. Hall focused on television discourse and compared it to a circuit. According to him , "Language and media do not reflect the real, but simply constructs something similar on our behalf." This constructed meaning is, however, fully realized only after the audience must have read it (Hall, 1973, p.2). So, unlike many previous theories that did not factor the audience in as an important part of the communication process, Hall's theory clearly attributes to the audience the power to change the meaning of a message in order to fit their social context. Consequently, Hall described communication as constitutive of two processes: encoding and decoding. The meaning encoded in a message by the author is not necessarily the meaning that will be decoded by the audience (Hall, 1973). "The audience receives the creative work done and perceives its content in either similar or different ways. The meaning of the message can change in the way they see it fit according to their social context" (Procter, 2004, p.11). To better understand this encoding-decoding dynamics, these two aspects of communication will be examined more details.

- i. **Encoding:** Encoding is the making and sending of a message with the intention that another person will comprehend it. The encoded messages usually contain shared symbols (signs or language) as

well as rules common with other people. So in encoding a message, the encoder has to bear the receiver (decoder) in mind, putting into consideration how he/she may perceive the message. There must be shared signs and language rules. At this stage of production of the message, the sender uses verbal cues, signs, and body language that he/she believes the person or group receiving the message will understand (Hall, 1973). The production must follow rules, and more specifically, language rules in order to convey its message (Procter, 2004). Without this, the message and system will suffer and become unsuccessful.

For instance, a person encoding a message in newspaper must comply with shared language rules including spelling, grammar and semantics. In addition, he/she must comply with specific technical rules special to newspaper including format and graphics. Without this, the communication may fail (Davis, 2004). In other words, the encoding ought to be realized within a shared space of signification.

However, encoding is not the end of communication because it is only one aspect of creating meaning. Though the person sending the message may believe that he/she is communicating unambiguously, the message may still be understood differently by the decoder given that meaning is not fixed, it is subject to varying readings (Davis, 2004). Another way to state this is that given that the encoding process is done by the sender alone, his/her individual ideologies and beliefs may colour the message as a result of which the audience will decode the message differently if they do not share those ideologies and beliefs (Davis, 2004). For this reason, Hall (1973) feels that the decoding end of the communication “circuit” deserves as much attention as the encoding end.

- ii. **Decoding** – The decoding of a message refers to how effectively someone can receive and understand a message. It can be a result of verbal messages yet does not always have to be. It is possible to be pictures or media, emotions, or even body language. For example, if someone is talking louder and their face turns, it can be inferred that perhaps they are angry. Procter (2004) observes that for Hall, decoding is the most important part of a communication process, and that recognising the role of decoding is Hall’s most significant contribution because many other previous theories did not pay attention to it all.

The decoding end of the communication “circuit” is the level of reading of the sent messages by the audience also called the decoder. The most basic principle here is that decoding can be said to be successful only if the message sent by the encoder is completely understood as intended. This is when the encoding and the decoding end does not suffer disconnect between them, thus allowing the communication “circuit” to be complete (Hall, 1973). This is what Hall means when he argues that messages sent with verbal/non-verbal cues don’t bring the same result always as intended by

the sender; it may indeed bring an altogether different meaning. In this case, a distortion has occurred as the audience comes out with a different understanding, a different take on the message (Hall, 1973).

Once a message is sent, the recipient is presented with messages, signs and cues that have been pre-coded. However, there is never solely one received message as the audience must add meaning and rebuild or recreate the message (Hall, 1973). Regardless of whether or not the message is one on one or to a crowd, decoding is all about receiving, absorbing and understanding the information that is being passed on. For the process to be successful, the received (or decoded) message must be the exact message that was encoded and then result in the appropriate process or act. When a message is received and understood this way, “preferred reading” has occurred because what is understood is what the encoder wants understood (Hall, 1973). On the other hand, the audience may read an entirely different meaning into the message. In this case, Hall (1973) considers the circulation as never transparent as the meaning changes as a result of factors like age, mood, gender, experiences, backgrounds and economic standings, which make audiences decode the messages in different ways.

Ultimately, according to Hall (1973), audience decoding of a message will resolve into any of the following three readings: dominant reading, negotiated reading and oppositional reading. Each of these readings is a product of certain factors that operate at both the encoding and the decoding ends of the communication circuit.

- **Dominant Reading**

Dominant reading occurs when the audience takes the message as given; when meaning is accepted as encoded by the source. This reading is the simplest of them all; the encoder sends their message through, the decoder receives it, understanding it and absorbing the ideology encoded in it in exactly the same way intended by the encoder (Davis, 2004; Procter, 2004).

In dominant reading, the producer or author’s message is successfully conveyed, and the reader has the “dominant thinking,” interacting, accepting, and understanding the intended message of the media. There are usually no misunderstandings, and quite often the receiver has the same ideologies and beliefs. In order for this to be successful, the message must be clear, and when this happens it is considered to be positive because the producer’s message is successfully sent and received (Procter, 2004). A dominant reader is not critical in reading the message; they are not skeptical, unsuspecting, thus literally swallows the message and the intended meaning.

- **Negotiated Reading**

Negotiated reading occurs when the audience accepts the meaning encoded in a message but with some critical disposition. The decoder does not swallow the meaning, rather they negotiate with it. For instance, an audience may be convinced that television content, such as pornography, is immoral but may still go on to view it. This way, the encoder's message is accepted by the decoder even though it goes against their personal convictions (Davis, 2004; Procter, 2004).

Another possible way a negotiated reading could occur is that a decoder reacts with a mixture of acceptance and rejection. Here, the audience understands the text and does not agree or disagree wholly, but instead it is possible that their opinions differ, at certain parts. Usually they do this because they see what the sender is trying to get across, yet they hold their own interpretation and views on other parts or create their own rules and scenarios (Hall, 1973). In negotiated reading, the decoder is not totally accepting or totally rejecting the meaning built into a message by the encoder, rather they are sieving through the message, taking some while rejecting some.

- **Oppositional Reading**

Negotiated reading occurs when the audience rejects the meaning encoded in a message. The audience fails to accept the author's viewpoint as encoded in the message. They understand the text as intended by the encoder, yet completely rejects the messages conveyed. Instead, they change and add their own meaning to it, which is usually opposite of what the sender meant and opposite to the dominant thinking or view. Many times, it is because it is not relatable to them, the structure does not reflect their society, it is controversial, or they simply disagree so they do not understand it in the same sense (Hall, 1973).

In essence, an oppositional reader is a disagreeing reader. Their reading contradicts the values and beliefs which the encoder intended to be read by receivers of the message. Oppositional reading is thus the direct opposite of dominant reading (Procter, 2004).

However, it has been noted that dominant, negotiated and oppositional reading are not always mutually exclusive. A single decoder can experience a mixed reaction of being a dominant, oppositional, and negotiated reader in a particular instance of message consumption, all depending on particular circumstances of the communication process in question. Thus, message decoding is ultimately a quite complex moment with different variables intervening and which may result in mixed reading.

Nonetheless, the Reception Theory has been criticized for what is seen as its emphasis on the dominant ideology. Contemporary trends in media production and distribution tend towards increasing audience participation in content creation. For instance, reality television shows involve audience voting while new media technologies have enabled more audience participation in traditional media. Consequently, the theory is seen as deficient for viewing the media-audience relationship in its holistic form (Nightingale, 1996;

Murdock, 1989). “Audience participation has increased dramatically in contemporary television, addressing the dominant reading and offering opportunities for varied outcomes. The rising popularity of reality TV shows is a good example of a larger audience participation” (Fiske, 1997, p.34).

In conclusion, the audience Perception Theory is considered relevant for examining audience exposure and response to media discourse on dangers and measures against plastic pollution. Media discourse on plastic pollution, like other media messages, is a product of encoding. However, in line with the postulations of the Audience Reception Theory, this encoded message will be subject to decoding during which the audience may understand the message as intended by the encoder or understand it in a different way, which implies that a distortion has occurred.

Research Design

This research was designed survey. Survey was chosen due to the nature of variables and big population under investigation.

Area of the Study

The area of the study was the South-East geopolitical zone of Nigeria. It comprises five states of Abia, Anambra, Ebonyi, Enugu and Imo. It is populated by Igbo speaking people and dominated by the Christian religion.

Population of the Study

The population of this study was all state civil servants in South-East geopolitical zone of Nigeria. The population numbered 32, 148.

Table 2
Sampling Frame

S/N	State	Population of civil servants
1.	Abia State	5, 856
2.	Anambra State	6, 761
3.	Ebonyi State	5, 670
4.	Enugu State	6, 532
5.	Imo State	7, 239
TOTAL		32, 148

Source: Offices of Head of Service of Respective States

Sample Size and Sampling Procedure

The sample size for the survey will be determined by referring to the scale of sample size adequacy as suggested by Comrey and Lee (1992). The scale is as presented in Table 3.2 below.

Table 3
Scale of sampling adequacy According to Comrey and Lee (1992)

S/N	Sample Size	Adequacy
1.	100	Poor
2.	200	Fair
3.	300	Good
4.	500	Very good
5.	1, 000	Excellent

The researcher settled for 500 which is rated as “very good” by Comrey and Lee (1992). To select the sample unites, the multi-stage approach was used. At the first stage, the researcher selected three states out of the five in the South-East region. The selection was made by simple random technique. The five states were listed in alphabetical order, then a table of random numbers was used to select three: Anambra, Ebonyi and Imo states.

The second stage involved selecting five clusters (ministries/departments/agencies) from the state secretariat of each of the three selected states. The researcher took this decision for convenience of sampling given that duty posts of civil servants are scattered across the local governments and towns of each state. Concentrating on state secretariats, made for a more definite frame of reference in conducting the sampling. Besides, the bulk of the civil servants for each state are concentrated in the state secretariat. The randomly selected clusters were as follows:

Anambra State: (1) Ministry of Housing & Urban Renewal, (2) Ministry of Information & Culture, (3) Office of the Head of Service, (4) Ministry of Environment, Beautification and Ecology, and (5) Ministry of Health

Ebonyi State: (1) Ministry of Health, (2) Rural Water & Sanitation Agency, (3) Ministry of Information & State Orientation, (4) Ministry of Agricultural and Natural Resources, and (5) Ebonyi State Scholarship Board

Imo State: (1) Ministry of Justice, (2) Imo State Orientation Agency, (3) Ministry of Finance, (4) Imo State Hospital Management Board, and (5) Ministry of Agricultural and Natural Resources

The third stage involved random selection of sample units from each of the clusters (ministries/departments/agencies). First, the total number to be selected from each state was arrived at using the following computation:

$$X = \frac{n}{N} \times \frac{500}{1}$$

Where X = number selected from a state

n = population of the civil servants of the state

N = Total population of civil servants in the 3 selected states

The number of civil servants selected across the states is as shown in Table 4 below.

Table 4
Sample Distribution

S/N	State	Number of Units Selected
1.	Anambra State	172
2.	Ebonyi State	144
3.	Imo State	184
TOTAL		500

The number allotted to each state was distributed evenly across the five clusters (ministries/departments/agencies) selected. Where there were remainders, the cluster(s) to which they would be allocated were decided using a random procedure.

Analysis of Data and Discussion of Findings

Table5: Respondents' Exposure to Discourses on Plastic Pollution via Mass Media

	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	455	94.2%
No	9	1.9%
No Answer	19	3.9%
Total	483	100%

While Table 5 indicates respondents' exposure to discourses on plastic waste generally, Table 8 shows the number that have got exposed to these via mass media. The data indicate that 94.2% were exposed to these discourses through mass media as against 1.9% that did not. In other words, just about 2% of those that were exposed to the discourses did not get the exposure through the media. Hence, mass media was a dominant source of exposure to discourses on plastic pollution for most of the respondents.

Table 6: Respondents' Channels of Exposure to Media Discourses on Plastic Pollution

Response	Radio/TV	Newspaper/Magazine	The Internet
Yes	29.6%	13.0%	92.3%
	N = 143	N = 63	N = 446
No	64.4%	81.2%	2.1%
	N = 311	N = 392	N = 10
No	6.0%	5.8%	5.6%
Answer	N = 29	N = 28	N = 27
Total	100%	100%	100%
	N = 483	N = 483	N = 483

Table 6 shows that 29.6% of the respondents were exposed to discourses on plastic pollution via radio/television, 13% were exposed via newspaper/magazine, while 92.3% got their exposure through the Internet. Thus, the Internet emerged as the most recurring channel through which the respondents were exposed to discourses on plastic waste. This finding tends to reflect the growing influence of online media as a source of information among users in Nigeria. Among the factors giving impetus to this reliant on the Internet for news and other forms of information is the fact that it is an all-encompassing platform were all other information channels, such as newspaper, radio and television, converge (Ikechukwu, 2015; Layefa, Johnson & Taiwo, 2016).

Table 7: Specific Media Discourses on Plastic Pollution Exposed to by Respondents

Response	Causes of plastic pollution	Dangers of plastic pollution	Measures against plastic pollution	Others
Yes	88.8%	94.6%	90.1%	89.2%
	N = 429	N = 457	N = 435	N = 431
No	1.4%	0.2%	4.1%	3.9%
	N = 7	N = 1	N = 20	N = 19
No	7.7%	5.2%	5.8%	6.8%
Answer	N = 37	N = 25	N = 28	N = 33
Total	100%	100%	100%	100%
	N = 483	N = 483	N = 483	N = 483

Table 7 shows that the specific media discourses on plastic pollution the respondents were exposed to; in other words, the themes of the messages of plastic pollution they encountered. The data indicate that 88.8% were exposed to discourses on causes of plastic pollution, 94.6% were exposed to those on dangers of plastic pollution, 90.1% were exposed to those on measures against plastic pollution, while 89.2% were exposed to other discourses. The foregoing suggests that media discourses may have dwelt more on the

implications (dangers) and solution (measures) to plastic pollution than on other issues. This a very likely scenario given that plastic pollution has posed a serious environmental and health problem to humankind (United Nations Environment Programme, 2018).

Table 8: Media Discourses on Plastic Pollution Most Repeatedly Exposed to by Respondents

	Frequency	Percentage
Causes of plastic pollution	2	4.0%
Dangers of plastic pollution	18	3.7%
Measures against plastic pollution	455	94.2%
No Answer	28	5.8%
Total	483	100%

Table 8 shows the media discourses which the respondents were most repeatedly exposed to; in other words, they ones they found most recurring. The data indicate that 4% identified causes of plastic pollution as the most recurring media discourse, 3.7% found dangers of plastic pollution as the most recurring, while 94.2% found measures against plastic pollution as the most recurring discourse. This time, most of the respondents clearly identified measures against plastic pollution as the most repeated discourse on plastic pollution in media; an arguably predictable situation given that the whole discussion about plastic pollution is ultimately geared towards arriving at a solution.

Table 9: Genres of Media Discourses on Plastic Pollution Exposed to by Respondents

	News	Features / Articles	Editorials/ opinions/ commentar ies	Interview s	Discussion Programm es	Documentari es	Campaigns	Others
Yes	87.4% N = 422	90.5% N = 437	6.8% N = 33	20.9% N = 101	18.8% N = 91	5.8% N = 28	66.5% N = 321	16.6% N = 80
No	6.8% N = 33	3.7% N = 18	87.6% N = 423	72.7% N = 351	75.1% N = 363	88.4% N = 427	28.0% N = 135	77.0% N = 372
No Answer	5.8% N = 28	6.2% N = 30	5.6% N = 27	6.4% N = 31	6.0% N = 29	5.8% N = 28	5.6% N = 27	6.4% N = 31
Total	100% N = 483	100% N = 483	100% N = 483	100% N = 483	100% N = 483	100% N = 483	100% N = 483	100% N = 483

Table 9 shows that 87.4% of the respondents were exposed to media discourse on plastic pollution in the form of news, 90.5% by way of features, and 6.8% by way of editorials/opinions/commentaries. Similarly, 20.9% were exposed to the discourses in the form of interviews, 18.8% in the form of discussion

programmes, 5.8% in the form of documentaries, 66.5% in the form of campaigns, and 16.6% by way of other genres. Thus, features/articles, news, and campaigns were the most recurring genres in which the respondents encountered media discourses on plastic pollution. Instructively, news constitutes the primary genre of mass media (Daramola, 2003), while features are an extended form of news (Eyiuche, 2003). On the other hand, campaign represents a direct attempt to influence someone, to achieve attitude and behaviour change (Akpoghiran & Okoro, 2014). The foregoing underscores the significance of these genres emerging as the most recurring messages of plastic pollution the respondents were exposed to.

Findings

Findings indicated that state civil servants in South-East Nigeria were exposed to media discourses on plastic pollution specifically via radio, television, newspapers and the Internet, with the Internet, however, being the recurring channel. The study further found that the specific discourses the civil servants were exposed largely related to the causes, dangers, and measures against plastic pollution. While the civil servants dominantly gave preferred reading to these media discourses on plastic pollution, their exposure to these discourses appeared not to have significantly influenced them to adopt the recommended environmental practices against plastic pollution.

Conclusion

In view of the above findings, the research concludes that media discourses on plastic pollution have arguably proved useful in terms of enhancing awareness and knowledge of plastic pollution among state civil servants in South-East Nigeria, especially in relation to its causes, dangers and measures to against it. However, it would appear that these discourses, irrespective of sufficient exposure and preferred reading of them by the state civil servants, have largely not been effective in terms of bringing about actual behaviour change.

Recommendations

Recommendations

In view of the above findings and conclusion, the researcher makes the following recommendations:

1. Environmental campaign (especially in relation to plastic pollution) in South-East geopolitical zone and indeed all parts of Nigeria should emphasize adoption of recommended actions and the benefits of so doing. This is given the finding that exposure to media messages on plastic pollution did not appear to have significantly influence the desired practices among the audience.
2. The respective state civil service commissions in the South-East should initiate measures to sensitise civil servants on issues of plastic pollution. This may come by way of seminars, conferences and workshops where emphasis should be more on adoption of healthy practices to checkmate plastic pollution.

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The foregoing affirms the widely held view in media effect scholarship that exposure and positive reception of media messages would not necessarily trigger the intended behaviour (Potter, 2012; McQuail, 2010). In the instant case, the respondents positively received the messages they got from the media regarding plastic pollution, its causes, dangers and measures against it, but this seemed not to have actually resulted in positive behaviour